

***Cryptoblabes gnidiella*, an azolla pest on rice in India**

S. Sasmal and J. P. Kulshreshtha, Entomology Division, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRRI), Cuttack 753006, India

Use of azolla, an N-fixing fern, is increasing in India. Effective insect control is essential to successful azolla cultivation. *Cryptoblabes gnidiella* Lep. Pyralidae is a major pest of azolla and sorghum in India, but has not been reported to attack rice.

During azolla multiplication in transplanted rice fields at CRRRI in 1983 rabi and kharif, *C. gnidiella* larvae moved from the azolla mat onto rice tillers, joined 3-4 leaves or folded a single leaf, formed a pupal case, and pupated (see figure). The larvae did not feed on the rice leaves. Three to seven larvae pupated in each rice hill depending on the level of azolla infestation. Infested plants looked similar to leafroller-infested plants. The pupal period lasted 7 to 12 d. □

Rice leaves folded by mature *C. gnidiella* larvae, Orissa, India, 1983.

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A method for holding eggs of rice insect pests for parasite emergence

A. T. Barrion, and J. A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, IRRI

The most common technique for holding insect eggs for parasite emergence is placing the cut plant part in a petri dish lined with moistened cotton or filter paper, or inside a test tube with a small amount of water at the bottom and plugged with cotton on top. Two problems occur: 1) rice leaves dry in a week, and 2) parasites become tangled in the cotton wadding. We developed an improved method (see figure) that keeps leaves green for 15 d, which is sufficient for parasite emergence. The freshly cut leaf with eggs is put inside a vial which is plugged with wet tissue paper. The vials are kept open end down in a jar or basin with 5 mm water for continual wetting. □

Setup for prolonged rearing of insect eggs on a cut rice leaf.

Effect of soil moisture and burial on germination of *Cyperus difformis* seeds

R. T. Lubigan, IRRI; B. L. Mercado, University of the Philippines at Los Baños; and K. Moody, IRRI

Cyperus difformis L. is one of the commonly occurring annual sedge weeds in transplanted rice in South and Southeast Asia because it is a prolific seed producer. We studied the effect of seeding depth, moisture regime, and light on *C. difformis* germination.

Soil was placed in 10.2-cm-high, 7.6-cm-diam plastic cups. Ten mg of seeds were broadcast on the soil surface, mixed with the top 1 cm of soil, or planted 1 cm below the surface. The soil was saturated or flooded with 1 cm of water. The treatments were replicated three times in a randomized complete block design. Germinated seeds were counted 15 d after seeding. We studied the effect of different light intensities on germination in a separate experiment and found that light is needed for germination.

Under flooded and saturated conditions, seed germination was highest when seeds were broadcast on the soil surface and least when the seeds were placed 1

Germination of *Cyperus difformis* seeds as affected by seeding method and moisture regime. Means with a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

cm below the soil, indicating that light is needed for germination (see figure). This observation was confirmed in the other study where no seeds germinated when soaked seeds were kept in the dark.